

Quantification of the surface with nano-grass

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The purpose of this paper is to calculate A_a/A_p of the nano-structured surface where A_a represents the actual area and A_p is the projected area. The calculation method is a common edge detection developed by Canny [1]. The SEM of the focused nano-structured surface is shown in Fig. 1 (a) where the height of a single nano-grass h_{nano} was measured to be around $2.89 \mu\text{m}$. It can be seen that there are peaks and valleys in the nano-structured surfaces. Fig. 1 (b) with a scale bar shows the top view of the nano-structured surface where the white area is the peak area and the dark is the valley. The resolution of Fig. 1 (b) is 1280×870 . The scale bar in Fig. 1 (b) can help determine the length per pixel, which is $5.501\text{E-}3 \mu\text{m/pixel}$ length. Therefore, A_p can be calculated to be $33.6987 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Fig. 1. Relations of the focused nano-structured surface. (a) SEM of the nano-structured surface. (b) top view of the nano-structured surface with a scale bar. (c) the image for edge detection. (d) Results of the edge detection.

As the scale bar would interfere the edge detection results. Therefore, Fig. 1 (c)

without a scale bar was adopted for edge detection. Through the python code (see the supplementary file “edge_detection.py”), we can obtain the results shown in Fig. 1 (d).

A_a can be determined by $A_a = L_{edge} \times h_{nano} + A_p$ where L_{edge} was detected to be 50097 pixel length and L_{edge} was calculated to be $50097 \times 0.005501 = 275.583 \mu\text{m}$.

Therefore, A_a was calculated to be as $796.4366 + 33.6987 = 830.1353 \mu\text{m}^2$. At last,

A_a/A_p can be determined by $830.1350/33.6987 = 24.6340$.

Reference

[1] Canny J. A Computational Approach to Edge Detection. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 1986, PAMI-8(6):679-698.

Appendix

The code of the edge detection is show as follows:

```
import numpy as np
import cv2 as cv
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt

img = cv.imread('123.jpg',0)
img = img[:870,:]
edges = cv.Canny(img, 100, 200)

fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12,12))
plt.subplot(121),plt.imshow(img,cmap = 'gray')
plt.title('Original Image'), plt.xticks([]), plt.yticks([])
plt.subplot(122),plt.imshow(edges,cmap = 'gray')
plt.title('Edge Image'), plt.xticks([]), plt.yticks([])

plt.show()

cv2.imwrite('./1.jpg', img)
cv2.imwrite('./2.jpg', edges)
```